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Dust impact on photovoltaic/thermal system in harsh weather conditions

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Abstract

Dust causes losses in power generated by the PV modules as well as causes an increase in their temperatures. In this study, the photovoltaic/thermal (PVT) module dust heating effect was investigated using a spiral coil using for two PVT water cooling systems. One of the two systems was cleaned periodically (every two weeks) and the second was left polluted with dust. The practical tests were conducted in Sohar – Oman outdoor conditions for two months (July and August 2021). The two systems performance was compared with a PV module left without cleaning.

The dust accumulated on the studied systems caused a decrease in their average productivity. After 30 days, the clean PVT, polluted PVT, and conventional PV systems; yield was 61.17%, 46.96%, and 42.73%, respectively. After 60 days, the average daily energy generated was 60.00%, 38.18%, and 33.90% for clean, polluted, and conventional systems, respectively. Increasing the exposure period to external conditions caused an increase in the accumulated dust rate, resulting in a deterioration in the power output of both polluting PVT and conventional PV. In the periodic cleanliness of the PVT system, most of its performance was restored and its losses were limited. After 4 and 8 weeks, the yield losses for the conventional PV system were (9% and 20%), (2.5%, 3.3%) for the clean PVT system, and for the polluted PVT system they were (7.5%, 17.7%).

Keywords: Photovoltaic/Thermal; dust impact; solar energy; photovoltaic; thermal collector.

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Introduction

The hybrid photovoltaic/thermal (PVT) system is combined of a PV panel and thermal collector to produce both electricity and heat (Al-Waeli et al., 2017). PVT systems have recently been considered very interesting and used in many applications. It is witnessing rapid growth and it is considered one of the systems that provide and maintains electricity and heat at the same time (Alktranee, 2018).

PVT systems have been rapidly developed and studies are carried out in succession to enhance the cooling of the photovoltaic module and increase the heat gain from it. These systems can be classified based on the cooling fluid used as air (Elminshawy et al., 2019), water (Shalaby et al., 2022), nanofluids (Jidhesh et al., 2021), PCMs (Sheik et al., 2022), and finally nanofluid/nano-PCMs (Al-Waeli et al., 2020). The effect of these coolants focused on the thermal and electrical systems' performance was studied, as well as its economic feasibility. Ibrahim *et al.* (2010) and Kazem et al. (2020a) used a spiral flow-absorbing collector and concluded that it enhanced heat transfer is best when cooled by water and nanofluids compared to other Web and direct flow types collectors. Poredoš *et al.* (2020) studied the effect of three different channel geometries (bionic absorber, parallel and serial absorbers) on the electrical and thermal energy efficiencies of PV modules and PVT systems using ANSYS Fluent and MATLAB simulations. The authors concluded that the energy efficiency of a standalone PV cell and PVT systems were 9.2% and 12.7%, respectively.

Others have studied the effect of the nanofluid used to cool the system (the effect of both the base fluid and the type of nanoparticles added). Several base fluids were used such as water, ethylene glycol, propylene glycol, oil, and mixtures of them (Al-Waeli et al. 2019; Apmann et al., 2022). Many types of nanoparticles have also been studied, whether metallic such as gold (Li et al., 2022), copper (Diwania et al., 2022), and aluminum (Al-Waeli et al., 2019) or metal oxides as CuO (Kazem et al., 2022), Al₂O₃ (Rezvani et al., 2022), TiO₂ (Shah et al., 2022), Fe₂O₃ (Ezzi et al., 2022) and etc. In addition to studying the effect of different types of carbon nanotubes such as SWCNT and MWCNT (Gao et al., 2022). To improve the stability of nanofluids, many researchers have tested different types of surfactants that can be added to suspensions (Al-Waeli et al., 2019; Singh and Mital, 2021). Several studies have been conducted to determine the thermophysical properties of a wide range of nanofluids that have been proposed for cooling PVT systems. Most researchers found that the use of water can be efficient in cooling systems, especially in harsh hot weather, and at the same time, it is less expensive. So, in current study, water will be used as a cooling fluid. Also, the spiral flow collector connected to the photovoltaic module from its back will be used to extract the heat collected in it. Nasrin *et al.* (2018) conducted research on the PVT system and introduced a new design of thermal collectors that employed a MWCNT-water nanofluid as a coolant to improve the overall thermal performance. The coolant was circulated using a centrifugal pump. The solar radiation and ambient temperature heated the PVT system. Using the proposed collector, the heat was proportionately dispersed while maintaining the inlet temperature. The PV efficiency and the thermal performance had increased to 9.2% and 4.0-3.6%, respectively. Table 1 shows a review of some important studies in the field of PVT and their most important achievements.

Table 1: Literature review of PVT systems from 2010 – 2022.

Ref.	Location	Year	Study type	Type of PV technology	Type of thermal collector	Efficiency (%)		
						Electrical	Thermal	Total
Ibrahim et al. (2010)	Japan	2010	Analytical	-	Spiral flow	12.0	-	65.0
Huang, and Yen (2014)	Taiwan	2011	Analytical	-	Glazed PVT Collector	12.7	30.7	43.4
Alzaabi et al. (2014)	SHARJA H, UAE	2012	Analytical	Poly-crystalline	Oscillatory flow absorber	15.0-20.0	60.0-70.0	-
Hussain et al. (2013)	Malaysia	2013	Analytical	-	Honeycomb structure of the collectors	10.0-17.0	87.0	-
Kim and Kim (2014)	Germany	2014	Numerical	Mono-crystalline	Air based collectors	15.0	22.0	-
Fudholi et al. (2014)	Malaysia	2014	Numerical and experimental	Poly-crystalline	Web flow absorber, Direct flow absorber and spiral flow absorber	-	-	65.0
Wang et al. (2015)	China	2015	Analytical	-	Air based collectors	13.6	36.2	-
Buonomano and Vicidomini (2016)	Italy	2016	Numerical and	Poly-crystalline	Flat Glazed Collector	10.0	16.0	26.0

			experimental					
Zhang and Chen (2017)	China	2017	Numerical	-	Flat plate collector	-	-	42.8
Nasrin et al. (2018)	Pakistan	2018	Numerical	Monocrystalline	Compound parabolic concentrator	Increased by 3.6-4.0	Increased by 9.2	-
Sardouei and Mortezaipoor (2018)	Iran	2018	Numerical and experimental	Monocrystalline	Round-tube heat exchanger Square-tube heat exchanger Box-type heat exchanger	13.6	56.0	-
Abdulrasool et al. (2018)	Iraq	2018	Numerical	Polycrystalline	impinging jets of water	11.3	72.0	-
Dimri et al. (2018)	India	2019	Numerical	Monocrystalline	Thermo-electric cooler	Increased by 1.9–2.8%	Increased by 20.8–21.8%	-
Pang et al. (2019)	China	2019	Experimental	Monocrystalline	Sheet and tube	11.0	57.0	-
Misha et al. (2020)	Malaysia	2020	Numerical and experimental	Monocrystalline	copper tubes dual oscillating absorber	11.7%	59.6%	-
Razali et al. (2020)	Malaysia	2020	experimental	Polycrystalline	spiral absorber	4.1	-	-
Brahim and Jemni (2021)	Tunisia	2021	Numerical	Monocrystalline	Water heat pipes	12.5%	43.7%	56.2%
Senthilraja et al. (2021)	India	2021	Experimental	Polycrystalline	spiral flow absorber	9.1	33.8	-
Menon et al. (2022)	India	2022	Experimental	Polycrystalline	serpentine coil	14.58%	58.7%	-
Elangovan et al. (2022)	India	2022	Experimental	Polycrystalline	Direct flow	19.3	54.0	-

Table 1 illustrates a literature survey of some conducted studies on PVT. The following highlights can be noted:

- There are variable forms of PVT technologies used as well as variable methods for cooling PV cells.
- When the PV modules are overheated their electrical efficiency deteriorates, therefore, yield losses can be reduced through cooling to improve the efficiency.
- The most important parameters affecting the performance of PVT systems, which were discussed in the literature, are the technology of PV modules, the type of thermal collector, the type of cooling method, and the cooling fluids used. However, it is noted that these parameters have not been studied together, so the overlapping of their conflicting effects has not been investigated until thoroughly.
- Most of the focus has been on research conducted on efficiencies (electrical, thermal, and total). However, the focus has been less on cost and environmental impact.
- Dust impact was not considered in these studies. Much research has been conducted on the influence of dust on PV panels or solar thermal collectors separately. However, based on literature it seems that there is limited research conducted to examine dust effects on PVT (Zhao et al., 2022).

Accumulation of dust on the surfaces of PV modules reduces their efficiency. The studies on the effect of dust on PV modules have abounded in the literature. Dust suspended in the air causes solar radiation to break and scatter, forming a kind of shadow on PV modules (Kazem et al., 2017; Bernadette et al., 2021). Also, the accumulation of dust on the surface of the PV module prevents the passage of solar radiation to it, as it either reflects or absorbs the sun's rays (Fan et al., 2021). The amount of absorbed or reflected rays directly depends on the nature of the dust (its source and components) and the amount deposited on the surface (Alnasser et al., 2020). Some researchers studied the effect of dust accumulation for long periods of time on the surfaces of the PV modules to measure its practical effect on the resulted electrical efficiency (Zhao et al., 2021). Others have studied the effect of different types of dust-forming pollutants on PV modules. These pollutants include red soil, ash, sand, calcium carbonate and silica, etc. (Kazem et al., 2022). These studies showed the variation and difference in the levels of decrease in the electricity generated by the photovoltaic modules depending on the type of pollutant and its accumulated amount on the surface (Tawalbeh et al., 2020). Kazem et al. (2020) concluded that what determines the effect of dust on the efficiency of the PV module is the proportions of its main components. The researchers also studied the effects of several variables such as dust

properties, ambient temperature, humidity and tilt angle and direction of the photovoltaic module (Salamah et al., 2022). While others studied the effect of wind speed and topographical characteristics of the PV system construction site (Yariyan et al., 2022; Ramirez-Revilla et al., 2022). Dust accumulated on the surfaces of the PV modules can be cleaned naturally by the influence of rain and wind. However, in cases of drought and rain interruption for a long time, the daily power generation losses are magnified, sometimes reaching more than 20% (Mani and Pillai, 2010). In the literature, there are many studies on the effect of dust on the yield and efficiency of PV modules. Similarly, several studies investigated the effect of cleaning photovoltaic modules on their performance. The researchers studied the effect of periodic cleaning (Azouzoute et al., 2021), the method of cleaning (Cattani and Magrini, 2021), and the cleaning agent used (AlMallahi et al., 2022). Gürtürk *et al.* (2018) studied the damage that can be caused by dust accumulation on photovoltaic modules in addition to the damage caused by the use of dust removal tools. The study concluded that the maximum energy efficiency was 17.8%, while the exergy efficiency was 19.3% and the energy conversion was 19.6%. These results were achieved when using a squeegee. Table 2 shows some of the most recent studies and the most important findings.

Table 2: Literature review of dust effect on PV systems from 2016 to 2022

Ref.	Location	Study type	Type of PV technology	Dust impact	Critical findings
Mohd et al. (2016)	Malaysia	Experimental	Monocrystalline	15–35% reduction in electrical efficiency	Dust causes a deterioration in the amount of solar radiation falling on the panel, which leads to a deterioration in electrical efficiency. The efficiency deterioration with the deposited dust density is linearly related.
Bergin et al. (2017)	US	Experimental	Monocrystalline	17-25% reduction in electrical production	Dust and particulate matter (PM) from human activities have a negative impact on solar electricity production in India and China. The researchers estimated that PM is responsible for 1 and 11 GW of solar degradation and loss in both countries, respectively.
Xingcai and Kun (2018)	China	Numerical	-	It is currently possible to predict the solar radiation intensity and the dust deposition rate by developing of the capabilities of forecasting weather numerically significantly.	When predicting the transmittance of solar radiation in dusty atmospheres, it is important to focus on the particle material, dust density, and the distribution of dust particle diameter measurements.
Gholami et al. (2018)	Iran	Experimental	Monocrystalline	21% reduction in output power after 70 days without cleaning the panel	Dust accumulation on the PV module causes a deterioration in current and voltage. The deterioration in the open circuit voltage is limited compared to the deterioration in the short circuit current.
Tripathi et al., (2018)	India	Experimental	Polycrystalline	The short circuit current and output power of the PV module decreases from 0 to 40%, when dust accumulates at a rate of 0 to 11 g on the surface of the photovoltaic panel.	The surface temperature of the dusty PV module is increased by up to 12.32% compared to that of a clean panel under the same conditions.
Pan and Zhang (2019)	China	Experimental	Polycrystalline	Dust is deposited in various patterns on the glass surface of the photovoltaic module, affected by the type of coating or whether it is an exposed surface.	Dust is deposited on the bare surface of the solar panel with a size of more than 30 micrometres, while when coating this surface, the accumulated dust size does not exceed 10 micrometres.
Dhaouadi et al. (2021)	United Arab Emirates	Experimental	Polycrystalline	Dust accumulation on the panel reduced solar transmittance	The study showed that the rate of dust accumulation in the study area was in average 0.7 mg/week. Examination of

				by 30% after leaving the panel for 15 weeks exposed to outdoor conditions without cleaning.	the dust components found many minerals such as calcite, gypsum, and silica.
Hachicha et al. (2019)	United Arab Emirates	Experimental	Polycrystalline	Experiments inside the laboratory showed a linear relationship between the density of the accumulated dust and the generated capacity, with a decrease of about 1.7% per g/m ² .	There is a relationship between the accumulation of dust and the angle of inclination, as the resulting power deterioration increases by increasing the tilt angle at 0°, 25°, and 45°, within 37.63%, 14.11% and 10.95%, respectively. Outdoor experiments showed that the dust accumulation in a level of 5.44 g/m ² after exposure to external conditions for five months caused a deterioration of the generating capacity by 12.7%.
Ullah et al. (2020)	Pakistan	Experimental	Polycrystalline	For a measurement period between October and January, it was found that the rate of dust accumulation on solar panels in the study area is 0.8% per day.	From the chemical analysis of accumulated dust, high percentages of carbon and quartz were found in it. These results prove the bad effect of air pollution with PM resulted from human activities.
Chanchangi et al. (2020)	United Kingdom	Experimental	Monocrystalline	When examining the effect of the accumulation of 13 different samples of pollutants on the performance of the PV panel, the results showed that coal causes the worst degradation on the short-circuit current of the PV panel by 98%.	Among the 13 examined materials, coal powder caused the highest limitation of light transmittance and reduced short circuit current, which reduces the generated power by 98%, while salt deposition on the plate gives the least reduction in the generated power by only 7%.
Cheema and Ismail (2021)	United Arab Emirates	Numerical	Polycrystalline	The proposed model can estimate the dust effects on the output power by inputting data of ambient temperature, solar radiation, and dust accumulation rate.	The proposed model can predict the rate of dust accumulation and its influence on the power output of each season based on atmospheric data. Through this model, it is possible to determine the most appropriate periodic cleaning times for the PV system to increase its productivity.
Fan et al. (2021)	China	Numerical	Monocrystalline	A theoretical model was created to evaluate the dust influence on PV efficiency and compare it in practice using six pollutants with exposure of the solar panel to variable radiation intensities.	The results showed that the PV module's performance deterioration rate due to the dust accumulation depends on the type of pollutant for a case of low radiation intensity. The rate of deterioration of PV module productivity increases with increasing radiation intensity.
Liu et al. (2021)	China	Experimental	Monocrystalline	Dust particles of nano and fine sizes as well as coarse particles are distributed unevenly on the surface of the PV panel.	The origin of the dust particles that accumulate on the PV panels in the study is human activities such as industry and construction works. Most of these pollutants are transported by wind and traffic.

Kazem et al. (2022)	Oman	Experimental	Mono and Polycrystalline	The accumulation of 5 g/m ² of ash and calcium. Carbonate, limestone, cement, sulphur, sawdust and brown soil on the surface of monocrystalline PV panel cause deterioration in the yield of the board in the order of 12%, 6%, 6%, 7%, 3%, 4%, 4% respectively. For the second case (using polycrystalline panel with the same amount of accumulated dust), the degradation was 5%, 4%, 4%, 1%, 2%, and 2% for the same dust components, respectively.	The optimal manual cleaning method differs according to the type of panel (mono or poly) and the site. The study found that the best cleaning material to clean both PV panels types is the sodium solution with rubber brushes and cloth. Polycrystalline panels are affected more by the dust gradients tested than monocrystalline by 10% when dust accumulated 50 g/m ² and up to 5.28% when the accumulation 5 g/m ² . The researchers suggested periodic cleaning varies according to the location. For example, for the cities of Liwa, Sohar and Barka, a periodic cleaning period of 10 days was suggested when using polycrystalline panels. As for all the five cities studied, when using monocrystalline PV panels, the suggested period is 15 days.
Pan and Zhang (2019)	China	Experimental	solar cell covering glass	Dust deposited on panels glass is affected by various types of coatings, and it is as high as possible when the panel's glass is without coating.	The results showed that dyeing the glass with a coating of SiO ₂ nanoparticles reduces dust accumulation better than using a water-resistant silica sol coating. The reduction of solar transmittance of glass due to accumulated dust using the coating is reduced to an average of 25.4%.
Fan et al. (2022)	China	Numerical	-	The study proposed a model that estimates the effects of dust accumulation and concentration on the productivity of the photovoltaic system. The model takes into account the effects of wind speed and direction, concentrations of dust particles flowing and their deposition rate on CFD sheets.	The study developed an expression to calculate the rate of dust deposition using inputs such as wind speed and particle measurements. When the tilt angle of PV panel is increased, a spiral vortex of dust particles has a maximum length at the back of the PV panel at an air flow velocity of 3.9 m/s and when the angle of inclination of the PV panel is 45°.

From Table 2, the following points are highlighted:

- Monocrystalline and polycrystalline are the most investigated PV module, which proven the dust impact and provide the required information for comparison.
- From the literature, it is found that the investigations covered indoor, outdoor, natural, and artificial dust. It is found that most investigations are the outdoor tests for natural dust impact.
- The studies focused on the electrical performance without mentioning the thermal impact. Also, the main studied parameters are efficiency and power.

In this study, the dust impact on PVT systems has been investigated for different flow configurations. The aim of the study is to evaluate the effect of dust accumulation on a PVT system on its electrical and thermal performance. The study was conducted in the harshest weather conditions in the study area to ensure the validity of this system for use in such areas. Two spiral flow collectors and one conventional PV system have been installed and tested in terms of dust impact. The experimental study was conducted in Sohar, Oman. Dust accumulated on the PVT for two months (July, and August 2021) to measure the performance parameters for the studied period, evaluated, and compared with the standalone PV system. Dust impact on electrical and thermal efficiencies has been calculated, evaluated, and discussed. The study results are compared with similar studies for conventional PV, since there is no such study for PVT systems.

Experimental Setup

A. Photovoltaic/Thermal system description

Three photovoltaic modules (one conventional PV and two PVTs) were insulated on the engineering building at Sohar University roof. The PV module for the tested systems has a capacity of 100 W monocrystalline technology, which the study by (Kazem et al., 2022) proved that its use in the study area is better compared to polycrystalline modules. The two PVT systems, have a spiral flow collector, which the study by (Kazem et al., 2020a) claimed that its use in the study area resulted in better yield compared to direct and web collectors. Moreover, to evaluate the dust influence on PVT system, the used cooling fluid is water.

Copper pipes were attached and connected to the back of two solar modules through which water passed. Once the water passes through the tubes, the cooling process of the solar modules begins. Three temperature sensors are connected: (1) a temperature sensor to measure the surface temperature of the solar module; (2) a thermal sensor to measure the inlet water temperature; and (3) a thermal sensor to measure the water leaving the modules.

Each module in the PVT system is connected to a water tank and pump for easy delivery of water inside the pipes. The process of cooling the water outside the solar modules is done by connecting each system with a heat exchanger, where the water outside the solar modules passes through it to enter again inside the water tank and goes again inside the solar modules and so on.

The hot water coming out of the heat exchange is utilized by connecting it to a fan to create solar dryer. For the outputs of the solar modules, are connected separately to a resistance of 100 ohms and a battery, and to read the outputs are done via the sensors, and Arduino, which is programmed and read by the computer as shown in Figure 1.

(c)

(c)

Fig. 1. Schematic of (a) conventional PV, (b) Photovoltaic/Thermal systems, (c) the studied systems photo, and (d) Spiral configuration.

B. Materials and Components

The components that were brought into use during the experiment are illustrated in this section. Further, a brief explanation is given to have a clear idea about the component and its operations. Copper pipes are used, which were designed to produce spiral flow configuration is shown in Figure 1(d). This flow configuration was the most suitable for the conditions of the study area as it proved by (Kazem et al., 2020a). The pipes are welded to the back of the PV modules to produce the cooling effect of PVT. The back of the PV panel was coated with a thin layer of silicone oil before installing the heat exchanger. The tubes are fully welded to prevent air gaps that reduce heat transfer and to ensure complete contact between the tube and the back of the PV panel causing efficient heat transfer. Temperature sensor connected to measure water inlet, and outlet temperatures. Also, the water flow meter type Hunter HC (US made) measures the water mass flow rate. Cold water circulates through the tubes using a water pump (3-30 HP and a maximum speed of 2900 rpm). It absorbs the excess heat in the PV and transfers it to the external heat exchanger with fan used to release the heat. An Arduino type (contains ATmega328P – 8 bit AVR microcontroller) was used. The Arduino used is accurate, programmable and low in cost. It is also characterized by flexibility and ease of use. As for the photovoltaic modules tested, they are monocrystalline type, with a total generated power of 100 W, short circuit current of 5.94A and open circuit voltage of 22.32 V. The two PVT systems and conventional PV are connected on an aluminium frame horizontally.

C. Study Area

Sultanate of Oman is located between latitudes 16° 40' N and 26° 20' N and longitudes 51° 50' E and 59° 40' E (inside the solar belt). The climatic conditions in the north of the Sultanate are desert, while it is subtropical in the south. Kazem *et al.* (2013) showed that Oman average irradiance is 5.197 kW/m²/day, while the daily irradiation period ranges from eight hours/day in winter to 10.5 hours/day in summer. Oman map is illustrated in Figure 2(a) while Figure 2 (b) manifests the hourly change in Sohar - Oman irradiance.

Sohar is one of a high suspended dust density sites in Oman, and therefore the dust accumulation rate on photovoltaic modules is high as clarified by (Kazem and Chaichan, 2019). This dust high density is due to the presence of several factories that emit pollutants near the city, in addition to the power plant. Figure 2(c) shows the dust accumulation rate on a PV module dedicated for this purpose. This period can be considered the highest in the amount of dust accumulated on the PV units, so it was chosen to conduct the study as it is considered the harshest during the year. Kazem and Chaichan (2016) and Kazem and Chaichan (2019) studied Sohar city accumulated dust's components and found that the proportion of 55% to 65% of it is silicon oxides of desert source. Dust in Sohar is also characterized by high levels of sulfur, soot and volatile particles. The concentrations of dust components vary with the seasons, weather conditions and wind movement.

(a)

Fig. 2. (a) Map of Oman, (b) Sohar city mean hourly irradiance (H.A. Kazem, Khatib, and Sopian 2013) and (c) dust accumulation rate through the study period.

D. Performance evaluation criteria

(i). Electrical yield

The methodology used to measure PV electrical performance is the current, voltage, power, efficiency, I-V, and P-V characteristics (Tanesab et al. 2016). The two PVTs and conventional PV modules' electrical parameters were measured and recorded for further evaluation, and comparison. The dust accumulated on the PVT and PV modules and parameters reductions were measured and evaluated. The measurements were conducted during the summer season when the solar irradiance is the highest in Oman. The I-V and P-V curves were measured for the outdoor systems under real operating conditions. The IEC 60891 method has been used to transpose between the standard test condition (STC), and the real operating condition (Li et al., 2021).

The electric power is expressed as:

$$P_{max} = I_{mp} \times V_{mp} \quad (1)$$

Where I_{mp} , V_{mp} , and P_{max} are current (in A), voltage (in V), and power (in W), respectively.

The electrical efficiency (η_e) of PV module is calculated using the formula below:

$$\eta_e = \frac{P_{max}}{G \times A_{module}} \quad (2)$$

Where (G) is the solar irradiance (in W/m^2) and A_{module} is the PV module area (in m^2).

Also, current and voltage can be calculated as follows:

$$I = I_1 + I_{sc1} \left(\frac{G}{G_1} - 1 \right) + \alpha \cdot (T - T_1) \quad (3)$$

$$V = V_1 - R_s \cdot (I - I_1) - k \cdot I \cdot (T - T_1) + \beta \cdot (T - T_1) \quad (4)$$

Where I , I_1 , V , and V_1 are the current (in A) and voltage (in V) at STC, and ORC, respectively. Also, α (in $A/^\circ C$) and β (in $V/^\circ C$) are the current, and voltage temperature coefficients, respectively. G , G_1 , T , and T_1 are the irradiance (in

W/m²), and temperature (in °C) at STC, and ORC, respectively. R_s and k are the internal series resistance (in Ω), and curve correction factor of PV module (in $\Omega/^\circ\text{C}$), respectively.

The normalized weekly average of the daily peak output power of dusty modules is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Weekly Average Normalized Value} = \frac{\text{weekly average daily peak power output of dusty modules}}{\text{weekly average daily peak power output of clean modules}} \quad (5)$$

(ii). Thermal performance

The key equations for the thermal energy performance parameters used in this study are:

$$\text{Useful energy } (Q_u) = \text{Absorbed solar energy} - \text{thermal losses} \quad (6)$$

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{Q_u}{G \cdot A_c} \quad (7)$$

Where Q_u is the heat gain (in W), A_c is the collector area (in m²) and G is irradiance (in W/m²). This energy is the heat gain:

$$Q_u = A_c [S - U_L (T_{pm} - T_a)] \quad (8)$$

Where S is the absorbed solar irradiance and U_L is the heat transfer coefficient. T_a and T_{pm} are the ambient and panel temperatures (in °C), respectively. S is evaluated by the formula:

$$S = (\tau \cdot \alpha)_{av} \cdot I_T \quad (9)$$

The absorbed and lost energies are calculated as follows:

$$\text{Absorbed energy} = A_c \cdot F_R \cdot S \quad (10)$$

$$\text{lost energy} = A_c \cdot F_R \cdot U_L (T_i - T_a) \quad (11)$$

Where F_R is the heat removal factor and U_L is the heat transfer loss coefficient, T_i is the inlet fluid temperature and T_a is the ambient temperature.

Substituting equations (10) and (11) in equation (6) to get:

$$Q_u = A_c \cdot F_R \cdot S - A_c F_R U_L (T_i - T_a) \quad (12)$$

Which can be simplified to

$$Q_u = A_c \cdot F_R \cdot [S - U_L (T_i - T_a)] \quad (13)$$

Experimentally, the collector performance evaluated using fluid inlet (T_i), and outlet (T_o) temperatures along with mass flowrate (\dot{m}) as follows:

$$Q_u = \dot{m} \cdot C_p \cdot (T_o - T_i) \quad (14)$$

Where C_p is the specific heat of the fluid and the efficiency is calculated as follows:

$$\eta_i = \frac{\dot{m} \cdot C_p \cdot (T_o - T_i)}{A_c \cdot G_T} \quad (15)$$

Results and discussion

A. Electrical performance

The systems were tested for a period of 60 days, leaving the first PVT system to be polluted by dust accumulation during this period. The second PVT system was cleaned periodically (every 15 days) before sunrise using sodium solution, rubber brushes and fabrics, according to (Kazem et al., 2022) study, which was conducted in the same study area and advised using periodic cleaning of two weeks for monocrystalline PV modules. Figure 3(a) and (b) show the energy comparison of the tested systems after 30 and 60 days of dust accumulation. Measurements are taken from July 1 to August 31, 2021. Solar radiation is the highest in these two months (summer season) with a slight difference. However, the first observation was that the energy degradation of the clean spiral PVT system was limited, and its decrease in the dusty system and the conventional PV module was clear and impressive. Also, more deterioration occurred after 60 days compared to 30 days without cleaning. The productivity improvement of the clean PVT system is due to the decrease in the temperature of the solar cells and the absence of dust accumulation impact due to periodic cleaning. The average percentage of energy generated per day after 30 days was 61.17%, 46.96% and 42.73% for clean, polluted, and conventional systems, respectively, compared to the maximum power at standard test conditions. However, after 60 days, the average daily energy generated was 60%, 38.18%, and 33.9% of PV energy for clean, polluting, and conventional systems, respectively. In a PVT system, the temperature of the solar cells is reduced by cooling, but on the other hand, dust accumulation reduces productivity. The difference between the clean and polluted PVT systems is caused by the accumulation of dust and the failure to clean the polluted system. Comparing the productivity of the clean and polluted systems after 30 days (July operation), the power loss was 14.21% while after 60 days (July and August operation), the loss was 21.18%. The increase in the rate of energy losses after 60 days of operation compared to 30 days didn't double as expected. However, the accumulation of dust for a long time (as in the case of 60 days) causes the volatilization of large particles with low adhesion strength. While the nano-sized particles adhere to the solar module surface and bonding with their respective nanoparticles, resulting in a uniformly distributed coating as (Chaichan and Kazem, 2020) claimed. The solar radiation intensity was somewhat higher in August than in July with higher relative humidity. The availability of these two factors together with dust can form a thin layer of

oozing clay above the surface of the PV panel. This layer is difficult to clean. It acts as an insulator that prevents light from reaching the photovoltaic cells. Therefore, during this month, it is preferable to modify the periodic cleaning days to be every 10 days instead of 15 days. The measurements during this month showed that the cooling performance of the circulated water decreased somewhat. The energy production decreased more in August due to the increased accumulation of dust. When comparing the results between the PVT and PV systems, a clear difference in the productive power appears. Exposure of traditional PV modules to both high temperatures without cooling and accumulated dust without cleaning caused losses of 18.44% and 4.23% through July and 26.10% and 4.28% through August operation, compared to clean and polluted PVT systems, respectively. The deterioration of productivity and the obvious losses in the used conventional PV system require periodic cleaning, which is mandatory for this case.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Power production after (a) 30 days and (b) 60 days of dust accumulations.

The normal weekly average of the daily maximum energy output was calculated for the three tested systems adopting Equation (5). The first day of testing was considered when all tested systems were clean. Figure 4(a) shows the results showing the trend of decrease in the generated power. The output power decreases with increasing periods for all systems. However, for the periodic cleaning PV module, it regained its power after periodic cleaning and the losses were limited. It was found that the normal limit of dusty PV after 4 and 8 weeks is 9% and 20%, respectively. However, the clean PVT system showed a smaller decrease for the same period (2.5%, 3.3%). Here, it should be emphasized that

the reduction of polluting PVT system is high compared to the other PVT system. For the same period, the deterioration was around 7.5% and 17.7%. Since both PVT systems are using the same cooling method to reduce the temperature of their PV modules. Therefore, the temperature effect can be neutralized, and the deterioration in the generated power (for a polluted PVT system) is a result of dust accumulation. Figure 4(b) shows the effect of dust accumulation on the three systems after eight weeks at midday (noon). The solar radiation was 879 W/m^2 . It was found that there was a significant reduction in the PV current compared to PVT systems. Also, the clean PVT system has the maximum I-V characteristics in comparison to other systems. Moreover, current is affected more by dust accumulation than voltage.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 (a) Normalized dusty output power per weeks, (b) I-V characteristics after 8 weeks.

B. Thermal performance

Figure 5 shows the thermal results in terms of dust impact after 60 days. The temperature increases during the day and peaks in the midday so that as expected the cell temperature increases as Figure 5(a) clarifies. The standalone PV panel

appears the highest temperature of 63.41°C at noon. Also, the clean, and polluted PVTs showed the same pattern with less temperature in the middle of the day at 47.44 °C, and 59.01 °C, respectively. The clean PVT shows a flattened curve with a range of 48.31°C - 40.26 °C. As the dust is reduced the solar irradiance approaches the modules, and it is observed that temperature differences are low between different models. While similar studies used clean systems such as those (Kazem et al., 2020a), the differences were significant between these systems.

Figure 5(b) compared different systems' ability to extract heat and cool the solar cells. It is found that the difference between the studied PVT systems was clear. The clean PVT system reduced its module temperature by 5.5% less than the polluted PVT module. The previous observation illustrates that dust accumulation increased the polluted PV module temperature, which reduced the cooling credit compared with the clean PVT system.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 Temperature comparison for (a) solar cells, (b) systems water inlet and outlet.

Figure 6 shows a comparison of the three studied systems' overall efficiency after 60 days of dust accumulation. The clean PVT system was higher than polluted one and conventional PV systems by 76.9% and 355%, respectively. However, as the PV system has no thermal efficiency, its overall efficiency is just the electrical one. Comparing the two PVT systems efficiencies illustrate that the polluted system's curve is relatively flattened, which is different compared to the clean PVT system. This result is in line with the results of both (Al-Nimr and Dahdolan, 2015; Kazem et al., 2020a).

Fig. 6 Studied systems overall efficiencies.

C. Comparison with literature

It is difficult to compare current study results with literature because of the differences in studied PVT module type, rating, configuration, location, solar irradiance, period, design elements, etc. However, Table 4 illustrate a comparison of current study results with literature in term of observations and key findings. The comparison has been considered with references investigated clean and dusty PV modules and thermal collectors. Also, the comparison extended to clean PVT systems from the literature.

Table 4. Comparison with similar studies for one-month period.

Ref.	Key finding
Zakzouk, 1984; El-Shobokshy and Mujahid, 1985	The dust impact causes a large change in the PV efficiency and short circuit current, while the open-circuit voltage did not change. The study concentrated on the influence of temperature and dust deposition on the solar cell and how it affects the modelling of the series resistance of the cell model.
Garg, 1974	The study found a 30% and 2% transmittance reduction for horizontal and vertical positions, respectively. Also, the authors claimed a high reduction in a plastic case.
Pettit and Freese, 1978	The study found that to limit the dust deposition loss to a single waveform of the specular reflector, a portable directional reflectometer can be used.
Mastekbayeva and Kumar, 2000	Due to dust accumulation on the solar cell over 30 days' period, it is found that the transmittance dropped from 87.9% to 75.8%.
Cabanillas and Munguía, 2011	The study investigated three solar cell technologies (polycrystalline, monocrystalline, and amorphous silicon) in terms of dust accumulation impact. It is found that the efficiency average monthly reduction is 13.0%. However, power decrement and the effect on I-V characteristics are different for the three technologies.
Wakim, 1981	The dust accumulation impact of solar photovoltaics was investigated in terms of performance parameters. It is found that PV efficiency decreases up to 17.0% in 30 days.
Said and Walwil, 2014	Dust accumulation impact on PV transmittance, I-V characteristics, voltage, and the current was investigated. It is found that general observation is the decrease in performance. Also, the efficiency decreases up to 7.0% in 30 days. The dust type and characteristics are primary elements specify the impact level.
Current study	The accumulated dust caused a significant deterioration in the productivity of the conventional PV module and reduced this productivity for a polluted PVT system compared to a PVT system that is cleaned periodically.

Conclusion

Dust causes a loss in the produced power of PV modules as well as the case of high temperatures on the PV surface. The overheating impact on PV modules can be reduced by using PVT systems. However, the effect of dust remains an additional factor in reducing productivity. The dust has a heating effect on PV modules that have been studied in a very limited way. In this study, two PVT water cooling systems were used employing a spiral coil, while one of them was kept cleaned periodically (every two weeks) and the second was left to become polluted with dust in the Sohar-Oman. The two systems performance was compared to a standalone PV panel left without cleaning. The period of observation and measurement was for July and August 2021.

The study shows that the effect of the accumulated dust on the studied systems is clear and effective, as its productivity was on average after 30 days 61.17%, 46.96%, and 42.73% for clean, polluted, and conventional systems, respectively. However, after 60 days, the average daily energy generated was 60%, 38.18%, and 33.9% of standard PV energy for clean, polluting, and conventional systems, respectively. The yield of contaminated PVT and PV systems deteriorates by increasing exposure time to external conditions without cleaning. While the periodically cleaned PVT system, regained most of its performance after periodic cleaning and its losses were limited. After 4 and 8 weeks, the yield losses for the conventional PV system were (9% and 20%), (2.5%, 3.3%) for the clean PVT system, and for the contaminated PVT system it was (7.5% and 17.7%).

Declaration of interest statement

“We the authors declare no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers’ bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript”.

Conflict of Interests

“The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper”.

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